

Performance Monitoring and Evaluation of the Programs

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Abstract:- The study was conducted to examine the performance monitoring evaluation of the programs in terms of strategic, core and support functions and identify the challenges encountered in achieving the functions. The study employed a mixed-methods research design. The Department Performance Commitment Review (DPCR) of the academic units from the academic year 2018-2020 served as the secondary data to answer the objectives of the study. An interview was conducted among the participants regarding the challenges met by the programs in achieving the different functions. Document analysis was also used to carefully review and analyze the performance of the programs, and to assess whether the major final output targets of the 3 functions were met. Findings revealed that the quality assurance under strategic functions were fully achieved against its target while research, extension and production resulted from partially achieved to not fully achieved. Most of the core functions were fully achieved, although 2 of the indicators were partially achieved. It further shows that the support function on streamlined process for fast delivery of services was partially achieved and there was a delay in the submission of documents and the deliverables were not done on time as well. This may be explained by the multitasking of the faculty members in the university. Moreover, the programs were consistently ranked the timeframe of document submission as the most challenging indicator in achieving the department performance commitment review where they have difficulty in meeting the deadlines. The programs resorted to generate more support both from internal and external stakeholders in order to comply the expected deliverables.

Keywords:- Core Functions, Department Performance Commitment Review, Performance Monitoring Evaluation, Strategic Functions, Support Functions.

I. INTRODUCTION

All throughout the program's life, performance monitoring evaluation can be used to track the quantity, the quality and characteristics of services and clients. It would measure the targets and accomplishments of the program in carrying out the various functions. In addition, the performance monitoring would describe whether the intervention planned is of quality and whether the desired outcomes are being achieved. It will further provide information to the stakeholders pertaining to the performance of the program.

The Civil Service Commission have issued a Memorandum Circular no. 6, series of 2012 in relation to the Guidelines in the Establishment and Implementation of Agency Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS) in which the agencies shall institute a Performance Evaluation system based on objectively measured output and Performance Evaluation System developed by the CSC. The SPMS focuses on measures of performance results that are reviewable over the period of the implementation of the CSC Road Map vis-à-vis targeted milestones and provides a scientific and verifiable basis in assessing organizational performance and the collective performance of individuals within the organization.

According to Family Health Outcomes Projects Planning Guide (2013), a monitoring evaluation does not measure whether the program interventions caused the observed effects and that to evaluate the "success" of a program is based on the assumption that the program theory has been proven and thus, the program can achieve success. Therefore, the purpose of the evaluation is to assess whether the program is being implemented correctly as designed and to monitor whether the desired results are arising. Further, performance indicators measure the change of the results indicated in a results framework and this will convey whether key objectives are achieved in a meaningful way for performance management (USAID, 2010).

The study of Striteska (2018) revealed that only few companies and agencies have a highly developed strategic performance monitoring system (SPMS) where the most neglected area is the existence and quality of the process for reviewing, modifying and implementing performance measures. It is therefore an endless challenge for every agencies to continually improve their strategic performance monitoring system (SPMS). Thus, redesigning the SPMS needs to be considered to appeal to intrinsic motivators and focus on individual improvement. Performance management processes should be streamlined and a more agile methodology adopted. (Torero and Mojica, 2020).

Few studies revealed that lack of performance feedback, inadequate resources, unrealistic expectation, poor communication (Kaupa, 2020), harassment, biasness in rating, lack of attention, unfair treatment to employee are some of the main problematic issues in achieving a good performance rating. All of the members in an organization has equal role to perform. The input efforts, output results, focus specification in terms of quality and quantity products/services, feasible cost and time factor are all responsible for the expected performance (Panda, 2011). Along the same vein, the study of Shilongo (2018) on

challenges in the implementation of the performance management system showed that lack of goal setting, poor alignment of personal objectives with organizational goals, lack of communication and strong leadership (Rajendran, 2021), lack of trainings and personal development (Kaupa, 2020), lack of monitoring, reviews and performance feedback, lack of change management initiatives and no reward for exceptional performance are the challenges encountered by the employees and unit heads pertaining to achieving the performance outcomes. A recent national survey of Wise (2015) on the emerging challenges facing school administrators revealed that the responsibilities today have changes compare to five years ago and that the job has increased in complexity. Accountability is one of the major challenges facing the administrators in the United States such as too many meetings, too much paperwork, too many time-consuming useless tasks, finding time to supervise instruction, fewer and fewer resources and support, yet more and more work.

In Bukidnon State University, the Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS) is implemented, where all the colleges and units are mandated to submit an Office Performance Commitment and Review (OPCR) and Department Performance Commitment and Review (DPCR) for the different programs quarterly. The Performance Management Team (PMT) shall conduct an evaluation of the actual accomplishments against the targeted performance in which performance measures include the effectiveness/quality, efficiency and timeliness. However, as per the record, there is no monitoring of the actual performance against the target objectives or standard that the program is meant to achieve to serve as basis in the assessment of individual staff members or perhaps, what particular success indicators have not met by the program in general basis for any developmental interventions. As emphasized by the CSC Memorandum Circular No. 6, series of 2012, monitoring and evaluation mechanisms should be in place to ensure that timely and appropriate steps can be taken to keep a program on track and to ensure that its objectives or goals are met in the most effective manner. With such consideration, this study is purposely designed to provide evidence-based findings on the performance monitoring evaluation ratings of the programs as to its level of attaining the targets and its challenges met in achieving the different functions.

➤ Objectives

- To examine the performance monitoring evaluation rating of the Programs in terms of status in achieving the following functions:
- ✓ Strategic Functions
- ✓ Core Functions
- ✓ Support Function
- To identify the challenges met by the programs in achieving the:

- ✓ Strategic Functions
- ✓ Core Functions
- ✓ Support Function

➤ Conceptual Framework

To deliver on its mandate, the performance of the program must be constantly monitored to ensure that the strategic aims and priorities are being achieved (NCSE, 2016). Monitoring provides significant inputs for evaluation and therefore establishes part of the overall evaluation procedure and evaluation gives evidence of why targets and outcomes are or not being achieved (NAISIT, 2017).

In the strategic performance management system, the performance of each program can be measured and evaluated using the various indicators specifically on the three functions such as strategic functions, core functions and support functions.

The main concern of this research is on how the various programs of BukSU achieved the 3 functions as reflected in different parameters of the Department Performance Commitment Rating (DPCR). The challenges met by each program in achieving the functions will serve as basis for recommendations.

Fig 1 Conceptual Model Showing the Parameters of the Study

II. METHODOLOGY

The study employed a mixed-methods research design. The participants of the study were the chairpersons of the 15 programs from the 6 colleges in the university namely the College of Education, College of Arts and Sciences, College of Technologies, College of Business, College of Nursing and College of Administration. The Department Performance Commitment Review (DPCR) of the academic units from the academic year 2018-2020 was served as the secondary data to answer the objectives of the study. Participants were interviewed regarding the challenges met by the programs in achieving the different functions. Document analysis was used for objective #1 to carefully review and analyze the performance of the programs, and to assess whether the major final output targets of the 3 functions were met.

➤ *Ethical consideration*

The researchers observed proper protocol like securing the preliminary requirement of the university. Official letter of request was made in order to access documents and addressed it to the Office of the Vice President for

Academic Affairs. The letter of approval was then forwarded to the different colleges and programs. The researchers ensured that all the works of other authors will be properly recognized in the paper.

III. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

The DPCR serves as one of the performance monitoring and evaluation of the programs within the department. It is an instrument wherein various indicators are provided to measure the expected and actual accomplishments of the programs. There are three main parameters that the programs will be monitored and evaluated namely: 1) strategic function; 2) core function; and 3) support function.

The results and findings of the paper will be presented, analyzed and interpreted on the following pages.

➤ *Performance Monitoring Evaluation of the Programs in terms of Strategic, Core and Support Functions*

Table 1 Summary Table of Performance Monitoring Evaluation Rating of the Programs

Programs	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
Major Final Output															
1. Strategic Functions															
1.1 Quality Assurance	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	3	5	5	5	5	5
1.2 Research	3	3	3	1	1	3	3	5	1	3	3	3	3	1	3
1.3 Extension	5	3	3	3	3	3	5	3	5	5	5	5	5	1	3
1.4 Production	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	5	1	3	3	1	3	1	3
2. Core Functions															
2.1 Highly Qualified and Competent Faculty	5	5	5	5	5	3	5	5	5	5	5	3	5	5	3
2.2 Teaching Performance	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
2.3 Extensive academic linkage with other HEIs and partner agencies	5	5	5	3	3	3	5	3	5	5	3	5	3	3	5
2.4 Graduate with innovative and ethical leadership competencies	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
2.5 Local, National, International priorities and advocacies integrated in the curriculum	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
2.6 Satisfied Clientele	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
3. Support Functions															
3.1 Streamlined processes for fast delivery of services	5	5	5	5	5	5	3	3	3	3	3	3	5	5	5
Timeliness	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Legend: 5 = Fully Achieved, 3 = Partially Achieved, 1 = Not Fully Achieved, (1) = delayed/not on time

Table 1 displays the summary of results of the performance monitoring evaluation rating of 15 programs. For strategic functions, it showed that the quality assurance is fully achieved against its target. This means that all the programs in the university conformed with the national and international standards. These special programs are supported by the national government and other institutions such as AACUP, ISO, ISA and SUC Levelling. As further revealed, research, extension and production resulted from partially achieved to not fully achieved. The result implies that most of the programs have difficulty in achieving the targets set in the department performance commitment

review for research, extension and production indicators considering that these are 3 of the 4-fold functions of the university. It was also discovered that the publication of the research output and its utilization were very challenging to achieve. Likewise, only few of the programs have completed the Instructional Materials (IM) which have been copyrighted. This finding is supported by the study of Tindowen, et al (2019) that doing research is one of the major challenges encountered by the teachers, this would added to workload and burden. It is further emphasized that research is a stressful task, overlapping of activities and experience sleepless nights. Teachers have lack of time,

writing anxiety and inadequate knowledge in the conduct of research. Likewise, in the study of Sermona, et al (2020), a number of challenges met by faculty-extensionist from State Universities and College in the Philippines. These are particularly in the stages of conducting extension services such as hectic schedule of faculty, difficulty in crafting proposal, lack of cooperation from participants, procurement issues and unavailability of monitoring form.

For Core functions, it showed the full attainment of the 6 indicators, these are the teaching performance, graduate with innovative and ethical leadership competencies, local, national, international priorities and advocacies integrated in the curriculum, and satisfaction of clientele. This confirms that core function is indeed the major function of every program in the university. These are functions that implement and deliver the mandates of the university as identified by the university code. The other 2 indicators such as highly qualified and competent faculty, and extensive academic linkage with other HEIs and partner agencies were partially achieved. This indicates that some faculty members are still pursuing their post graduate degree programs and that the academic linkages and partner agencies of the other programs were only limited. Although, it is further shown, there has been a good number of programs whose faculty members are all trained and has achieved more than its target of the faculty with doctorate degree. In CHED

Memorandum Order No. 40, series of 2008, stressed out that all higher education institutions (HEIs) faculty must have at least masters degree in the fields in which they teach because the quality of education depends largely on the qualifications and competencies of the faculty. Moreover, the university through faculty development program has been providing assistantship to the faculty members to meet the requirements and to ensure quality education.

For Support functions, it revealed that the streamlined processes for fast delivery of services was partially achieved. The result denotes that some programs were not able to meet the standards and efficiency of the required documents being asked. Surprisingly, it was also revealed that there was a delay in the submission of required documents and the deliverables were not done on time as well. This may be explained by the multitasking of the faculty members in the university. According to the study of Alkahtani, et al. (2016), multitasking on the academic work gives a detrimental effect to the faculty members. It focused on the negative impact rather than the importance of attaining the skill and the ability of being effective multitaskers.

➤ *Challenges Met by the Programs in Achieving the Strategic, Core and Support Functions*

Fig 2 Challenges Met by the Programs in terms of Strategic Function

Figure 2 shows the frequency count and rank of the challenges met by the programs in terms of strategic function. Most of the programs considered timeframe of document submission as the most challenging part in making a DPCR. This means that the programs had a difficult time in meeting the deadlines of submitting the documents. In the article written by Lopez (2013), she pointed out that time management is a huge task for huge companies or offices. It shows that it is quite difficult for the offices to submit tons of documents on time. However, the programs able to deliver the tasks through team work.

To add, the result of the interviews of different Chairpersons presented more evidences that lesser number of faculty and their support play a vital role to achieve their targets. This finding is supported by the study of Zhang and

Usaho (2018) revealed that the poor organizational communication and lack of support of the faculty members are the most challenging part of being an administrator and that the division of labor and clarity of their task are clear. However, based on the data, the lack of support from the faculty has less bearing to the attainment of the strategic functions. This implies that collaborative support matters the most than just one entity in achieving the goals. Collaboration drives workplace performance effectively. It ensures that your work environment and all work-related activities will gear towards collaborative working set up participants in achieving the goals who were well-informed to act collaboratively stuck at their task longer than their solitary peers, had exhibited higher engagement levels, lower fatigue levels and a higher success rate (Gaskell, 2017).

Fig 3 Challenges Met by the Programs in terms of Core

The core functions had the biggest share in the DPCR. This is where most of major deliverables in the university are expected to require and submit. In the data of figure 2, timeframe of document submission got the highest frequency. This indicates that the programs find this indicator most challenging to achieve. The chairpersons explained that the faculty did the multitasks to cope with the deadlines. They further stressed out that teamwork in the programs fueled attainment of their expected targets. This result is supported with the study of Schmutz, et al., (2019) indicating that teamwork is positively related to performance of the employees.

In addition, lesser number of faculty, difficulty in retrieving of documents and some of the indicators are

beyond the control of the departments, posted the least challenged to them. This means that in spite of these challenges they are still able to deliver the expected accomplishments of their programs. Sadeep Kashap explained that there are common challenges in accomplishing the tasks, however, he singled out that keeping the team in the same page matters. This means that the number of employees will not matter much for as long as the employees will work productively as a team. Lipman (2017) added that helping to create a positive team environment where employees feel free to speak their minds and connect with each other is a bit more complex yet rational thing to do to hasten the delivery of results. These scenarios are also observable in the academe.

Fig 4 Frequency Count of the Challenges Met by the Programs in terms of Support function

The programs consistently ranked timeframe of document submission as the most challenging indicator in achieving the DPCR. This simply mean that the programs find this specific challenge need to be addressed immediately. In the article written by Hasan (2016), he pointed out that setting an unrealistic deadline and expectations may lead to failures. He further suggested that cohesion of the team is important in an organization. This further indicates that timeliness of document submission posed as the major dilemma of the programs.

The aforementioned scene, the programs resorted to generate more support both from internal and external stakeholders in order to comply the expected deliverables. Accountability is one of the major challenges facing the administrators in the United States such as too many meetings, excessive paperwork, too many time-consuming useless tasks, finding time to supervise instruction, fewer resources and lacking support, yet more and more work (Wise, 2015; Mulford, 2003).

In summary, the study of Shilongo (2018) on challenges in the implementation of the performance management System showed that lack of goal setting, poor alignment of personal objectives with organizational goals, lack of communication and strong leadership (Rajendran, 2021), lack of trainings and personal development (Kaupa, 2020), lack of monitoring, reviews and performance feedback, lack of change management initiatives and no reward for exceptional performance are the challenges encountered by the employees and unit heads pertaining to achieving the performance outcomes. Hence, with these challenges they encountered, the programs resorted to generate more support both from internal and external stakeholders in order to comply the expected deliverables.

IV. CONCLUSION

- Based on DPCR, most of the indicators of the 3 functions were fully achieved against its target. Although, difficulty of achieving targets set in research, extension and production were observed. However, under the support function, specifically the timeliness indicator, the submission of deliverables was not delivered on time.
- Timeframe of document submission is consistently ranked as the most challenging indicator in achieving the Department Performance Commitment Review (DPCR) of the programs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Intervention plan may be made to strengthen the faculty engagement into research, extension and production.
- Academic linkages of every program may be intensified through the support of the International Affairs of the University.
- The administration may consider the hiring of administrative aid or faculty associate for every program to assist the chairperson in preparing the necessary documents related to the different functions

and to ensure the on time submission of the documents necessary.

- Planning of activities in the university may be revisited so as not to overlap the deliverables.
- Collaborative efforts of the faculty members and support of other offices to the programs are encouraged.

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